

INFLUENCE OF DIFFERENT REPRESENTATION OF REQUIREMENTS ON IDEA GENERATION: AN EXPERIMENTAL STUDY

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ABSTRACT

The objective of this research is to understand how different representations of requirements influence idea generation in terms of quantity, addressment, sketch detail, novelty, and variety of conceptual sketches. Requirements are statements of need, desires, and wishes of the stakeholders that are used by engineers to frame the problem. Essentially, requirements are the *raison d'être* for any engineering project. As the requirements document provides constraints and criteria for a design, it defines and determines the success of a project. While there is research studying the effect of requirements on the conceptual sketch, little study has focused on the impact of different requirement representations on solution development. An experimental study was conducted with 52 fourth year mechanical engineering undergraduate students. Two design problems were formulated with three different representations: a problem statement with embedded requirements, a problem statement and a traditional requirement list, and a problem statement with contextualized scrum stories. Each student was provided each design problems with two different representations of requirements. It was found that the use of contextualized scrum story representations significantly affected the conceptual sketch in the novelty of solution fragments and addressment of requirements, while no significant change in variety, sketch detail, and quantity was seen. Also, the contextualized representation positively affected all metrics but the sketch quantity. Finally, it was found that quantity is not directly related to the number of requirements addressed in the sketches.

Keywords: sketching, requirements, design process, requirements representation, scrum, contextual sketch, agile

1 MOTIVATION

Product development is a cross-functional activity in which marketing, design, and manufacturing are central functions of the product development project [1]–[4]. The success of a product is attributed to the profitability of the product [3]. The goal of developing a successful product is not only the responsibility of the design team or the marketing team but also of all stakeholders. It is, however, difficult to assess profitability quickly and directly [1], [3]. Nonetheless, high performance along with the product development aspect of product quality, product cost, development time, development cost, and development capability are good indicators of economic success [1]. That being said, only a few companies are successful more than half of the time [1]. In 2006, only 34% of studied projects were successful with 13% failing due to incomplete requirements and 9% failing due to frequent changes in requirements [5]. Due to the importance of requirements in the success of a project, a lot of research has been devoted. However, minimal to no effort has been not allocated to the agile process for hardware design.

The goal of this paper is to consider whether the classical design process can be reworked using agile (scrum) process to attain more successful projects. The unit of analysis in the study is the concept sketches generated by different representations of requirements as evaluated against quantity, addressment, variety, novelty, and sketch detail [6], [7].

1.1 Design Process

Today, the traditional design method (stage gate) is still used in the industry, with some outliers using the agile process [8]–[10]. It is worth noting that “traditional” refers to the widely presented design process in many popular textbooks [1], [2], [11]. The traditional design method is a sequential process but an overlapping

process. The stages are problem definition, conceptual design, embodiment, detail design, and final design. It is a sequential process where requirements are gathered first and then used to drive concept generation [12]. This leads to a weakness in this process of being able to react to the changes [8], [13]. The agile process is an incremental and iterative process where the scope of time is fixed as opposed to work deliverable. Also, the product requirements are evolving through the design cycle, allowing a quick reaction to change in requirements. Evident in the result found by a consulting company, where software projects using agile process are twice as more likely to be successful [14]–[16]. Observing success in software design has made its way to hardware design.

1.2 Requirements in Engineering Design

The engineering design process is a general framework that assists designers in solving design problems. The first step of any design process is to define the problem. Some experimental evidence suggests that sketching solutions before detailing requirements may generate richer requirement documents [17], but this is not the approach traditionally taught [2], [12]. The development of requirements is a subset of a problem definition stage. Generating and managing requirements is a critical task in the design process as requirements are used to evaluate the success of the design project and serve as a basis for verification and validation. Requirements provide a systematic approach to select and remove a potential solution [18]. Design literature introduced a checklist [11], quality function deployment (QFD) [2], [19] and a combination of both to help establish requirements. In the scrum design process, a scrum story is written to convey the needs [8]. All of whom capture the voice of the customer [2], [8], [18]. However, they are represented differently, seen in Table 1.

Table 1 An example representation of a traditional requirement and a scrum story (Contextual)

Traditional	Contextual Story
The device must be <i>manually operated</i> .	As a user, I would like the device to be <i>manually operated</i> so <u>I can enjoy the peach picking process.</u>

In the traditional method, requirements follow the format of:

“The <system> <shall/must> <be/do> <modifiers>...”

While scrum stories are written as:

“As a < customer role or system > I want to < perform an action > so that I can <gain this benefit>.”

A scrum story can be defragmented into who this requirement is for, what do they want, and why do they want it [8], [20]. Also, the stories are expected to evolve during the project life cycle while the traditional list of specifications is ideally fixed in the traditional waterfall approach [11], [21], [22]. Another major difference is scrum stories provide justification and empathy for that requirement explicitly. Empathy in design is recognized as useful for generating better understanding of the problem [23]– [25]. As the representation of requirements is the first major difference between the processes, it is vital to explore the impact of the different representations on concept generation.

1.3 Sketching in Conceptual Design

Studies show seventy percent of life cycle cost is decided in conceptual design [26], though this notion has been questioned on the accuracy and verifiability [27]. Generally, though, it is canonically accepted that it is crucial to focus on the “fuzzy front end” of product development [28]–[30]. Several idea generation methods, such as brainstorming, storyboarding, Gallery Method, and C-Sketching, have been presented in the literature. Several of these rely on sketching is a tool for innovation and improvement in the ideation process [31]–[35]. The benefits of sketching are:

1. Speeds up reasoning [2], [32].
2. Ease of understanding [32], [34], [36], [37].
3. Concisely represents ideas [32].
4. Provides insight [17], [38], and
5. Help memory [2].

Therefore, a graphical sketch tool is used to assist the designer in generating quick ideas while being creative [39].

2 EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN

An experimental study was conducted to learn how different representations of requirement influence conceptual sketches. Three different conditions were presented in the study. First, the problem statement, it is where participants are given a problem statement with five embedded requirements. Second, the traditional representation is where participants were given a problem statement and a list of requirements. Lastly, the contextual representation is where the participants received the problem statement and requirements in the form of a scrum stories. Table 2 shows an overview of parameters and their method of control to avoid external impact on the study. The study was approved by the Clemson University IRB.

Table 2 Summary of observed parameters and method of control

Variable	Method of Control
Participant Experience	52 novice engineers from senior level design course
Student Differences	Packets were randomly distributed among students
Motivation for Effort	Created as a class assignment
Quality of Education	Same professor for all the participant
Experimental Environment	Unable to control due to COVID-19
Requirement and Concept Generation Familiarity	Lecture presented on requirements and concept generation before experiment
Packet Equivalency	Same two design problems used for all the packets and the same amount of time given for each design problem

Twelve experimental packets were developed based on the three different representations of requirements (problem statement, traditional, and contextual) with two design problems. Multiple

design problems were employed to increase the number of data points and to conduct within-participant analysis [40]. In Table 3, packet distribution is visible with its corresponding design problem and condition. From left to right, the first column introduces packet numbers, the next states which design problem will be encountered first by the participant, then the condition presented with the first design problem. Next columns introduce the second problem that the participant will encounter with the condition of the design problem following next. From packet 1 to packet 6, problem A is given first. Then for the next six packets (7-12), it is given second. This was done to control advantages or disadvantages, if any are present, based on the sequence of problems addressed by participants.

Table 3 Twelve packets with its corresponding design problems (A & B) and conditions (Problem Statement or Traditional or Contextual)

Packet Number	1 st Problem	1 st Requirement Representation	2 nd Problem	2 nd Requirement Representation	CU-ID Range	Number of Distributed Packets
1	A	Problem St.	B	Traditional	00-08	6
2	A	Problem St.	B	Contextual	09-16	2
3	A	Traditional	B	Problem St.	17-25	5
4	A	Traditional	B	Contextual	26-33	4
5	A	Contextual	B	Problem St.	34-42	3
6	A	Contextual	B	Traditional	43-50	2
7	B	Problem St.	A	Traditional	51-59	3
8	B	Problem St.	A	Contextual	60-67	5
9	B	Traditional	A	Problem St.	68-75	6
10	B	Traditional	A	Contextual	76-83	6
11	B	Contextual	A	Problem St.	84-91	5
12	B	Contextual	A	Traditional	92-99	5

2.1 Participants

This experiment was conducted with participants from the fourth year of mechanical engineering at Clemson University. All 52 participants were selected from one class (ME4010, Mechanical Engineering Design course) and were taught by one professor in the same section. ME4010 is a project-oriented course and was deliberately chosen since a basic understanding of the design process was needed. Other studies have used this population in past experiments [17], [41]–[46]. The participants were randomly assigned one of the twelve packets, seen in Table 3. The last two digits of each participant's Clemson Identification number (CUID #) were used to distribute the packets with a predefine range to avoid any bias. Further, the study was conducted online, requiring a predetermined distribution approach. The random assignment of the packets was done to avoid any discrepancy in individual differences between participants. The resulting distribution is seen in Table 4.

Table 4 Distribution of students (condition and problem)

Problem	Problem Statement	Traditional	Contextual
A	19	17	16
B	16	20	16
Total	35	37	32

2.2 Problem Statement

The design problems found in this study are recycled from previous design experiments. Problem A was obtained from an experiment studying relationship between design method, design activity and creativity [47]. Problem B was acquired from an experiment studying elicitation of requirement on idea generation in terms of requirement addressed [48]. These two problems were chosen based on how relatable the participants are with each topic and their initial similarities. The problems were modified to fit the experimental design, seen in Table 5.

Table 5: The two design problems

Problem A: Work Desk Problem
Emily is a freshman at Clemson University. She suffered an accident at age 10 which left her in a wheelchair. According to Clemson University, undergraduate students are required to stay on campus in their freshman year. Because of the rule, Emily will be staying in a dorm room on campus for the first year of her university career. Due to her disability and limited space in a dorm room, she has asked Clemson University to design a desk that will be able to alternate position and save space in the room. Having an ability to manipulate the desk to provide more surface area in the room will help Emily be safe and will be easy for her to navigate the room. She has few things that she would like the desk to have. First, it should have 2 states, desk state and non-desk state. Second, it should be manually operated and should take less than 10 seconds to go from state A to State B. Also, the desk should include a storage system for most commonly used office supplies (i.e., Pencil, paperclip, stapler etc.). The device must cost less than 100 dollars.
Problem B: Peach Picking Problem
Emma is a 19-year-old mechanical engineering student at Clemson. She suffered a car accident couple of years back which left her in a wheelchair. Before the accident Emma loved the outdoors and picking fruits with her family. During the next summer break, she and her family have decided to go picking peaches. Since she is in a wheelchair, she has a limited range of reach, especially for height. Due to this limitation, she cannot experience the pleasure of picking peaches with her family. For her 20 th birthday her family has decided to surprise her with a device that will help her pick peaches while in a wheelchair. The family has asked Clemson University to help design a device that will allow Emma, who is in a wheelchair, to experience the joy of picking peaches from the tree with her whole family. The family has few things in mind that they would like the device to accomplish. They would like the device to be manually operated, and it should be attached to the wheelchair. Also, it should not damage the fruit and fall on the ground while picking. Also, the device should not cost more than 100 dollars.

After the modification of the design problem, the two problems were subjected to a similarity test using several metrics [40]. The metrics include the number of word count, the number of characters, the number of sentences, the number of embedded functions, and the prompts reading level. The chosen problems are not technical. It is done to ensure novice engineers can understand and interpret each problem statement easily. Problem A and Problem B are both shy of 200 words and Flesh's reading level to be at 64. The characters and the number of sentences is similar, with problem B having two more sentences and 59 more characters than problem A. Design problems A and B each have five embedded functions. The summary of the similarity test is found in Table 6. The problem statement condition has five embedded functions, while traditional and contextual representations have ten requirements given.

Table 6 Similarity test summary

Problem	Words	Characters	Sentences	Embedded Function	Flesh Reading Test (out of 100)
A	191	861	10	5	64.75
B	196	920	12	5	64.65

Example requirements developed for Problem A are illustrated in Table 7. Each traditional requirement is reformulated into a scrum story styled requirement. It can be seen that additional words are required for recasting the requirements into the contextualized format, but the meaning of each requirement has been held constant. Ten requirements were derived for each problem, drawn directly from the original sources when possible.

Table 7: Example Requirements for Problem A

Traditional	Contextual (Scrum)
The system must have 2 states, desk state and non-desk state.	As a wheelchair user, I would like the system to have 2 state, desk and non-desk state so that I can maximize the space in my dorm room.
The system must be manually operated.	As an administrator, I would like the system to be manually operated so that the electrical bill and the maintenance cost is minimum.
The system must take ≤ 10 seconds to go from state A to state B and vice-versa.	As a wheelchair user, I would like the system to take ≤ 10 seconds to go from state A to State B and vice-versa so that I can quickly transition from minimum space to maximum for freedom.
The system must cost ≤ 100 dollars.	As an administrator, I would like the system to cost ≤ 100 dollars so that it can be installed in all the ADA rooms.

2.3 Procedure

An in-class experiment was set up to help us understand the impact of different representations. However, due to the Covid-19 pandemic, the experiment was conducted virtually. A survey software, Qualtrics, was employed to aid in supervising the experiment and collecting the data. The flow of the survey is as follows, with each step being completed leading to a separate section in the survey.

1. Students complete a consent form per IRB
2. Instructions are provided with opportunity to contact the study administrator with questions via chat. Participants are told to gather ~10-15 pages of copy paper and a dark pen for the sketching activity. They are told that the activity will take approximately 60 minutes. They are instructed in how to generate a unique identifier so that submitted sketches can be aligned with individual participants while maintaining anonymity of the participant.
3. The student enters the last two digits of their CU-ID. Based on the results; they are directed to one of twelve virtual packets.
4. The student is provided with the first problem prompt and requirement list as prescribed by the packet. A countdown is provided for 30 minutes of sketching solutions based on the information provided. Students are asked to upload scanned images of their sketches.

5. The student is provided with the second problem prompt and requirement list as prescribed by the packet. Again, 30 minutes are allowed to generate and submit the sketches.

As shown above, participants must provide consent, a unique identifier, and the last two digits of their CU-ID before moving on. A unique identifier, created from first two letters of participant mother's name, birth month and day, and last two digits of CU-ID, is used to avoid bias when analyzing the data. With last two digits of the CU-ID, participants can be assigned to a specific packet and to their corresponding experimental conditions (Table 3). Participants are timed automatically with a built-in timer in Qualtrics. A countdown timer was placed at the top and the bottom of the page for ease of time observation. Once the timer ends, it will automatically change over to the next page. Participants are unable to go back a page because it will restart the timer allowing for no control of the duration of the experiment. After the design problem, participants are directed to upload the sketches. A minimum of one and a maximum of ten sketch submission spots per problem were given. It is repeated for problem two as well.

3 RESULTS OF EXPERIMENT

Based on the procedure explained above, 186 concept sketches were generated by 52 participants. First, an analysis was done to determine whether sequencing of the problems had an effect on results. This was done with ANOVA and a significance level of 0.05. Results showed that there was no statistical difference ($p=0.845$) when evaluating the population of students receiving Problem A first or Problem B first. Further, it was shown that there are significant differences in results based on the problem. With these preliminary tests, further analysis was done to explore the creativity metrics of quantity, addressment, sketch detail, novelty, and variety.

3.1 Quantity

In this study, quantity is the total number of sketches generated by each participant from two design problems. Quantity is chosen because it is believed that generating more ideas will lead to a greater probability of generating "better" ideas [2], [6], [7]. Using the files submitted by the participants, an image file (.jpg, .png, .jpeg) and a document file (.pdf) are used to analyze this metric.

3.1.1 Quantity Coding Methodology

The participants submitted sketches in a pdf or an image file. A minimum of one file was required for a participant to move on to the next step. Many participants submitted multiple image files. However, some of the participants submitted a single pdf file containing multiple pages. A pdf file is converted into an image file (.jpg) using Adobe, where each page is counted as one image file. For example, a pdf file with five pages converts into five separate image files (.jpg). Each file counts as one sketch, unless otherwise stated by the participant as concept 1 or next concept within one submission or across multiple submissions or files. If stated within one file, then the file is split. If participants state that a concept spans multiple files, then the files are combined and count as one sketched solution. In this manner, the quantity metric is objective with no interpretation of the data for the researcher. After isolation of files, sketches are subject to an evaluation for their validity. To be valid, a sketch must address at least one requirement found in the design problem. If a sketch is not related to or addressing the design

problem, then it is not counted. For example, if the participant submitted three concepts corresponding to one, five, and zero requirements addressed, then the quantity value of two is given. This verification of submission can introduce some subjectivity to the quantity metric. Inter-rater tests are described for the addressment metric and will be discussed in the following section. In Table 8, the result of total number of sketches generated per condition and per problem is shown.

Table 8 Total number of sketches per condition and per design problem

Problem	No requirement	Regular Requirement	Contextual requirement
1	42	29	26
2	29	34	26
Total	71	63	52

3.1.2 Quantity Analysis Results

Once all the concept sketches for each participant were counted and recorded, it was then compared whether the number of sketches generated by an individual differ between each test condition. An analysis of variance (ANOVA; $\alpha=0.05$) was used to examine whether there was a significant difference in two of the three experimental conditions. It was hypothesized that both the traditional and the contextual representations of requirements would result in a greater number of conceptual sketches being generated as opposed to the condition problem statement. A p-value of 0.242, on the other hand, indicates that there is no statistically significant difference in the number of sketches generated by any of the experimental conditions. In Table 9, a summary of quantitative analysis is shown, and Table 10 provides an overview of the ANOVA results.

Table 9 Summary of Quantity value

Groups	Count	Sum	Average	Variance
Problem Stat.	35.0	71.0	2.03	1.44
Traditional	37.0	63.0	1.70	1.05
Contextual	32.0	52.0	1.63	0.758

Table 10 ANOVA result for Quantity

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	3.15	2.00	1.57	1.44	0.242	3.09
Within Groups	110	101	1.09			
Total	113	103				

Although there is no statically significant difference in the quantity of concept generated, on average, the problem statement condition yielded a higher number of concept sketches per student, 2.03, as opposed to the traditional representation, 1.70, and contextual representation with 1.63 concept sketches per student. It is important to note that there is no adverse effect on the number of concept sketches generated by having contextual or traditional requirements.

3.2 Addressment

The second metric used to analyze the sketches is addressment. Addressment metric measures how many

requirements the solution addresses [17], [41]. This metric is used as a substitute for quality [6] as it is more objective. Further, it is difficult to predict the ability of a solution to meet a requirement early in conceptual design [37]. A solution sketch might address one, a few, or all the requirements. Ideally, subsequent design tasks would include extracting solution fragments (or means) and creating morphological charts for combinatorial exploration of integrated solutions [49], [50]. Sketches that address more requirements are of greater value than those addressing fewer requirements as they can be segmented in the future into more fragments. Further, as requirements are used to evaluate the solution, those sketches that address more requirements are more complete [1]–[3], [11]. In this study, assessment measures, and number of requirements addressed by the participant.

3.2.1 Addressment Methodology

Each concept sketch generated by the participant was subjected to addressment evaluation. Only requirements that were explicitly stated or identified by the designer were counted with an example of the prescribed protocol illustrated in Table 11.

Table 11 Addressment protocol example

Requirements	Comments/Explanation
2 state, Desk and Non-Desk	The sketch must include visual sign of two separate states of the desk, or it must describe how the desk will accomplish the goal of being in desk state and non-desk state. As well as state if the requirement is mentioned.
Manually Operated	The sketch must mention or include visual signs that indicate manual operation. For instance, having a handlebar, rope, and/or cable to push or pull the desk for it to transition between states.

For specification of having multiple states (Desk and Non-desk), it must be visually or textually shown, “state 1” or “desk state” and “state 2” or “non-desk state” (Figure 1).

Figure 1 Example of addressment of requirement

An inter-rater reliability test was done with two coders to test the scheme. Cohen’s kappa result was 0.82 and was deemed acceptable. This is similar to previous tests of similar codes for addressment [17]. A single rater was then used to evaluate all the sketches.

3.2.2 Addressment Analysis Results

Sketches are examined for addressment using the protocol mentioned above. The overall results are found in Table 12.

Table 12 Addressment summary for each test condition

Groups	Count	Sum	Average	Variance
Problem Statement	71.0	180	2.54	1.17
Traditional	63.0	190	3.02	1.85
Contextual	52.0	165	3.17	2.11

A statistically significant difference in requirements addressed within each test group was hypothesized. An ANOVA ($\alpha=0.05$) is performed between all of the test conditions to verify the hypothesis. Table 13 shows the result of ANOVA.

Table 13 An ANOVA summary for Addressment

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F-crit
Between Groups	14.1	2.00	7.03	4.23	0.016	3.05
Within Groups	304	183	1.66			
Total	318	185				

From the analysis of variance, a p-value of 0.016 was obtained. It indicates a significant difference between at least two out of three pairs of the test conditions. To determine which pairs are significantly different, a post-hoc Fisher's Least Significant Difference (LSD) test was conducted. Table 14 shows the result obtain from LSD method.

Table 14 Fisher's LSD comparison for Addressment

Difference of Levels	Difference of Means	SE of Difference	95% CI	T-Value	Adjusted P-Value
Traditional – Problem St.	0.481	0.223	(0.040, 0.921)	2.15	0.033
Contextual – Problem St.	0.638	0.235	(0.174, 1.102)	2.71	0.007
Contextual - Traditional	0.157	0.242	(-0.319, 0.634)	0.65	0.516

According to Fisher's LSD, the problem statement condition is statically different from the contextual and the traditional representation with a p-value of 0.007 and 0.033, respectively. This suggests that there is an influence of having requirements in either form increases the likelihood of a participant addressing requirements within the sketches. However, no significant difference was observed between the contextual and the traditional representation in terms of requirements addressed per sketch. It was observed that the contextual and the traditional representation addresses a higher number of requirements as opposed to the problem statement condition (2.54 requirements) with contextual averaging highest, 3.17 requirements. To conclude, the representation of requirements does have an impact on requirement address within the conceptual sketch.

3.3 Sketch Detail

The third metric used to evaluate the sketch is sketch detail. The term "sketch detail" is derived from the complexity metric of [34]. Detail is defined in terms of line, shading, and annotation [34], [36], [51]. It is used to analyze sketches because it provides a quantifiable difference in the quality of the sketch [34]. This detailing metric has five levels. The simplest sketches where only the physical principle is shown without any other detail is level one. The most complex sketch with a three-dimensional view including shading, colors, dimensions, and annotation is level five.

The coding scheme for detail complexity is subjective. For instance, for level three the protocol state "dimension might be apparent" [34]. For this study, a sketch image analysis tool is developed to mitigate subjectivity.

3.3.1 Sketch Detailed Coding Methodology

Python is used to develop the code that returns a sketch detail value between 0 and 250,000. The flow of code is presented later in this section. All sketches are converted into an image file before they are analyzed. Then all image files are all visually inspected by a ratter to check if an image needs processing. The processing of an image may be necessary due to the objectivity of the analysis. The coding does not distinguish between an image with a border around the sketch inserted by an external source (scanning app), an image drawn on notebook paper with lines (Figure 2), or any other unnecessary information presented with the sketch in an image unrelated to the design solution. Therefore, a quick visual inspection of sketches is necessary.

Figure 2 Example of sketch submitted that was processed before analysis

To assist the rater in deciding when and how to process an image, a protocol is developed and is seen in Table 15.

Table 15 Sketch detail protocol for image processing

Reason	Action to take	
Large border A border is created by a scanning app on a phone; picture is taken from too far out	Crop an image	Crop an image until the border is eliminated and the edge of an image is at the edge of the paper, or edge of an image is at the edge of the farthest line or mark created by the designer
Unnecessary lines (notebook paper, graph paper, other marks not related to design solution)	Trace the sketch	Use a computer or a pen with a same thickness as a pencil and trace the image
Border or part of an image is dark could be due to lighting or miss alignment of sketch when taking a picture and the code will be mistaken it for a	Trace the sketch and apply a filter (only if it is traced on a computer)	Using a computer or a pen, with a same thickness as of pencil, trace the image. Then apply a filter if it is trace on a computer. (Figure 3) If the sketch is traced on a new copy aper no filter is needed.

line/ shading/ annotation		
Unable to see the sketch. (Sketch too light)	Trace the sketch	Using a computer or a pen, with a same thickness as of pencil, trace the image
Multiple concepts in one image	Split an image	Split an image into multiple images (same number as number of concept present). A copy of an image is made and cropped into the concept size. The border of each image is set at the farthest line or mark for that specific concept.

In a case presented in Figure 2, using the protocol, the image will be cropped near the edge of the farthest line or mark created by the designer of the sketch. Then it will be traced over to highlight the sketch. Finally, a filter will be applied. The picture in Figure 2 will convert into an image shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3 An Imager ready to be analyzed

Once all the images have been visually inspected and needed images have been processed, the automated analysis is completed. All sketches are compiled into a folder, then passed through the script. The steps of the script are:

1. Creates an output .CSV file where output value and file name are stored.
2. Creates the list of all the files ending in .jpg, .png, and .jpeg
3. Converts the image into a black and white
4. Resize to 500 x 500
5. Evaluates each pixel
6. Pixel value below or equal to 128 is converted to 0 (black pixel)
7. Pixel value above 128 is converted to 255 (white pixel)
8. Creates an image using the new pixel array and saves under the same name with added extension “_BW.png”
9. Reads the new image (_BW.png) for all the black pixel
10. Writes the .CSV file with the file name and Output black pixel value.
11. From step 3 to step 8 the given code is written in a loop and will run until all the file in the list (created in step 2) has been evaluated using the script.

Finally, a .csv file containing all the file names and their raw sketch detail values is created. The raw value does not correspond to the solution's true sketch detail value. The size of the image being analyzed determines the true sketch detail value. As a result, a larger image provides more room for discussion [34]. Therefore, a size factor is added. A true value for sketch detail is found using the equation:

$$\begin{aligned} & SSSSSSSSSh \ DDSSSSDDDDDD \ vvDDDDvvSS \ (SSDDSS) \\ & = rrDDrr \ vvDDDDvvSS \ (RRSS) * SSDDSSSS \ ffDDSSSSff \ (SSSS) \end{aligned}$$

Where the size factor is between zero and five, and the raw sketch value is from 0 to 250,000. The largest image with dimension 3456 x 4608 will have the largest space for discussion, therefore, a factor value of 5 is assigned. The smallest size of an image is 1000 x 451, which corresponds to a size factor of 1. In between size factors are assigned based on linear interpolation of maximum and minimum size of the image.

3.3.2 Sketch Detail Analysis Results

After the analysis of all the sketches was completed (Table 16), an ANOVA test was used to determine whether there was a significant difference between any experimental conditions in terms of the amount of sketch detail present.

Table 16 Summary of Sketch Detail analysis

Groups	Count	Sum (x10 ⁵)	Average (x10 ⁴)	Variance (x10 ⁷)
Problem Statement	71.0	8.39	1.18	3.77
Traditional	62.0	7.21	1.16	4.31
Contextual	53.0	5.59	1.05	2.43

Based on the result obtain from ANOVA (Table 17), it can be concluded that there is no statistical difference in any of the experimental conditions with the p-value of 0.469. However, Table 16 shows Contextual representation of requirements averages lower than the problem statement and the traditional representations of requirements. This difference can be studied in future experiments.

Table 17 ANOVA summary for Sketch Detail

Source of Variation	SS (x10 ⁷)	df	MS (x10 ⁷)	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	5.43	2	2.71	0.760	0.469	3.05
Within Groups	653	183	3.57			

Total	659	185				
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3.4 Novelty

The fourth metric observed was novelty. Novelty is an indicator of how unusual or unexpected an idea is compared to other ideas [6], [7], [52]. According to [6], a higher number of novel ideas indicates more exploration of the design space, which increases the chances of finding a unique or an innovative design solution. As a result, an improvement or innovation of a product will take place. The development of new and improved products will benefit society [47], [53]. Since the goal of product design is to innovate and be creative, it is vital to consider novelty [52]. For the goal of improvement and innovation, a higher novelty is desired [53]. A

solution is novel if the likelihood of discovering a concept fragment within the entire population of the sample is low. In this study, a solution fragment was novel if it was presented in sketches by less than three participants or less than five percent of the entire sample population [17], [41]. As a result, an *a posteriori* analysis was conducted.

3.4.1 Novelty Coding Methodology

To aid in coding concept sketch, a protocol was developed to identify solution fragments from all the concept sketches. An example of a protocol of what can constitute as a solution fragment for Problem B is shown in Table 18.

Table 18: An example of a protocol for what to consider a fragment for Problem B

Requirements	Comments/Explanation
Manually Operated	The sketch must include visual signs that indicate manual operation. For instance, the sketch contains a trigger to squeeze, having a rope or cable to push or pull, etc.
attach to a wheelchair	The sketch must contain visual or textual evidence that indicates device is connected to wheelchair. For instance, the device is strapped, clamped, bolted, pinned etc.
not damage the peaches	The sketch must contain a method or feature that prevents damage to the peaches. For instance the sketch indicates peaches are cushioned when being cut, shield, falls in compartment after it is cut, soft material is used to grab the peach, or vacuum suction, etc.
pick multiple peaches at a time	The sketch must provide evidence of multiple peaches being picked either visually or textually. For instance, to hold the picked peaches the sketch includes net, basket, compartment, multiple arms, multiple grabbers/claws etc.

A similar protocol was also developed for Problem A to identify solution fragments. The coder is advised to follow the following guidelines with the protocol for each of the design problems:

- Must be clearly identified or presented by the designer to count as fragments.
- Can address the requirement with multiple fragments
- A fragment can address multiple requirements

Following the guidelines and protocol, each sketch was coded, and fragments were noted for all the individual sketches. An example coding for a sketch is seen in Figure 4. For each requirement, the sketch is reviewed. If a requirement is addressed, the feature of the sketch that addresses the requirement is circled. The solution fragment for that requirement is recorded in the table. Thus, addressment and novelty are addressed concurrently.

Requirements	Solution Fragment	
1.) 2 state, Desk and Non-Desk	Flip Top	
2.) Manually Operated		
3.) ≤ 10 seconds to go from state A to State B and vice-versa		
4.) Cost ≤ \$100		
5.) Safe to Operate	spring - light when moving up	Locking mechanism
6.) require ≤ 10-pound force (lbf) to transition from state A to state B and vice-versa	spring - light when moving up	
7.) Have Storage	Built in pencil box	Additional fix wall storage
8.) 4.5 ft ² when in desk mode		
9.) Easy to Operate	push "harder"	
10.) Footprint of ≤ 1ft ² when in a Non-desk mode		

Figure 4 Example of a novelty coding for an individual sketch

An integrated morphological chart was developed with all the solution fragments identified from the sketches for each three conditions (and excerpt is found in Table 19).

Table 19 Example of Morphological chart for solution fragments

Requirements	Fragment		
2 States, Desk and Non desk	Foldable Top	Roll in and out	Elevates surface
Manually operated	Pull cable	Lift handle	
Have storage	Drawer	Wall Compartment	Built in compartment
Footprint to ≤ 1ft ²	Turns into Sofa	Bookshelves	

An inter-rater reliability (IRR) test was conducted to verify the coding scheme. The defining solution fragments scheme was found to be sufficient with the kappa value of 0.73.

To mitigate bias due to an unequal number of participants in all three conditions, an analysis was performed per requirements. Therefore, twenty ANOVA tests were conducted, ten for problem A and ten for problem B. Additionally, four more ANOVA tests were performed, they are as follows with corresponding test number, found in Table 21:

1. Test effect of experimental condition in Problem A (test number 21)
2. Test effect of experimental condition in Problem B (test number 22)
3. Test Problem A to Problem B (test number 23)

4. Test effect of experimental condition, an overall test (test number 24)

The rating protocol for assigning participant a novelty score is derived from [41]. To assign each participant a novelty score, rater is advice to follow the following protocol.

- 1) Count the number of participants that identified that fragment within their solution
- 2) If the number of participants is less than 3 (5% of 52) then define the fragment as a novel fragment
- 3) Count the number of times a novel fragment is used by a participant.

The value obtained in step 3 of the protocol is the novelty score for that participant. An example of the table generated is shown in Table 20.

Table 20: Novelty table for Problem A Requirement 7 (WD7)

WD-Problem Statement	WD-Traditional	WD-Contextual
0	0	0
0	0	1
1	0	0
0	0	0
0	0	0
0	0	0
0	0	1
1	1	0
0	0	0
1	1	0
0	0	0
0	0	0
0	0	0
0	0	0
0	0	1
1	0	
0		
1		

The first participant in Problem Statement group generated zero novel fragments, thereby scoring a 0. While the third participant generated one novel fragment, scoring a 1. A value of 0 does not indicate no fragment was generated. A novelty table was created for all twenty requirements, and an ANOVA test was performed.

3.4.2 Novelty Analysis Results

A summary table of the ANOVA ($\alpha=0.05$), and a mean comparison between the Problem Statement group (P), the Traditional Requirement Representation group (T), and the Contextual Requirement Representation group (C) for all the requirements is shown in Table 21. If the p-value is less than the significant level of 0.05, then a post-hoc Fisher's LSD analysis is performed.

Table 21: Summary table of an ANOVA test for Novelty

Test Number	Problem	Requirements	P-value	Comparison of Mean
1	A	WD1	0.324	P>C>T
2	A	WD2	0.039	C>P>T
3	A	WD3	-	-
4	A	WD4	0.428	P>C=T
5	A	WD5	0.019	C>T>P
6	A	WD6	0.784	C>T>P
7	A	WD7	0.557	P>C>T
8	A	WD8	0.114	C>T>P
9	A	WD9	0.620	C>T>P
10	A	WD10	0.145	C>P>T
11	B	PP1	0.154	C>T>P
12	B	PP2	0.271	C>T>P
13	B	PP3	0.889	T>C>P
14	B	PP4	0.520	C>T>P
15	B	PP5	0.669	C=T>P
16	B	PP6	0.260	P>T>C
17	B	PP7	-	-
18	B	PP8	0.433	T>C>P
19	B	PP9	0.653	T>C>P
20	B	PP10	0.325	C>T>P
21	A	All	0.020	C>P>T
22	B	All	0.123	C>T>P
23	A to B	All	0.768	-
24	A + B	All	0.019	C>T>P

There is not statistically significance difference in eighteen of the twenty requirements. Two requirements with a significant difference are WD2 (p-value of 0.039) and WD5 (0.019). Also, Problem A (test number 21) is determined to be different statically. A post-hoc Fisher's LSD analysis is conducted to determine which pair is significantly different. The results of LSD analysis for WD2, WD5, and Problem A are highlighted in Table 22.

Table 22 Summary LSD result for WD2, WD5, Problem A

Difference of Levels	WD2 (P-Value)	WD5 (P-Value)	Problem A (P-Value)
Traditional – Problem Statement	0.191	0.410	0.339
Contextual – Problem Statement	0.166	0.006	0.053
Contextual – Traditional	0.011	0.051	0.006

For WD2, it is determined that there is no statistical difference between the contextual and the problem statement (0.166) condition, and between the traditional and the problem statement (0.191) condition. However, the contextual representation is statistically different from the traditional representation (0.011). The contextual representation on average generated 0.430 novel fragments per participant as opposed to 0.240 novel fragments for the problem statement condition and zero for the traditional representation. Like WD2, there is no statistical difference between the Traditional and the Problem Statement condition (0.410) for WD5. However, a difference between the Contextual and the Problem Statement (0.006) condition is found. The Contextual and Traditional conditions are not found to be statistically different with a p-value of 0.051. But, with the significant level of 0.05, the difference in p-value is 0.001. It fails to reject the null hypothesis,

but it is of interest and will require further investigation. The Contextual (0.560) and Traditional (0.190) representation of requirements on average generated a higher number of novel concept fragments per participant compared to the Problem Statement (0.100) group.

Based on Fisher's LSD analysis for Problem A, the Problem Statement condition does not differ statically from the Contextual (0.053) and the Traditional representation (0.339). However, the Contextual representation is statistically different for the Traditional representation, with a p-value of 0.006. The contextual representation outperforms the Problem Statement and the Traditional representation condition with an average novel fragments per participant of 2.63, 1.53, and 1, respectively. The difference in p-value based on a significant level of 0.05 between the Problem Statement and the Contextual representation condition is 0.003, warrants further study.

The overall novelty of the experimental condition is determined statistically using the data point from both design problems. An ANOVA test (test number 24) is employed to check if there is a statistical difference between the experimental condition for generating novel concept fragments. Therefore, a novelty table is created by grouping the novelty score by experimental conditions for both design problems, yielding a total of 104 data points (52 for Problem A and 52 for Problem B). The test resulted in a p-value of 0.019, less than the significant value of 0.05. Therefore, indicating an alternative hypothesis of a significant difference between at least two of the experimental conditions. A post-hoc Fisher's LSD analysis is used to determine which representation is statically different.

Table 23 LSD for an overall result of Novelty

Difference of Levels	Difference of Means	SE of Difference	95% CI	Adjusted P-Value
Traditional – Problem Statement	0.175	0.377	(-0.573, 0.924)	0.643
Contextual – Problem Statement	1.060	0.391	(0.279, 1.83)	0.008
Contextual - Traditional	0.880	0.386	(0.114, 1.65)	0.025

The contextual representation is statically different from the Problem Statement and the Traditional representation of requirement. However, the Traditional and the Problem Statement condition are not statically different. Nonetheless, the Traditional representation yields a higher number of novel fragments per participant than the Problem Statement condition with 1.43 and 1.25, respectively. Therefore, the Traditional representation is suggested to perform better than the Problem Statement condition. Still, the Contextual representation of requirements results in the highest average of novel fragments per participant at 2.31 novel fragments.

3.5 Variety

The last metric used to evaluate sketches is variety. Variety is a measure of how well a design space has been explored [6]. An observation of a similar idea is an indication of low variety. Therefore, less likely to find a "better" solution [7]. Hence, high variety is desired. For this study, variety is the number of different idea groups that were generated for each requirement per participant [41].

3.5.1 Variety methodology

To obtain variety, each concept sketch is subjected to methodology mentioned in novelty for coding sketch for concept fragments. To assign each participant a variety score, the rater is asked to follow the following guidelines:

- Count the number of solution fragments participant used to address a requirement.
- Observe the experimental condition that the solution is for
- Enter the value obtain in the Variety table for a requirement to its corresponding experimental condition

Table 24: Example of a fragment table for Variety scoring

Participant	Sketch #	Solution fragments for PP1
1	1	Pull string to close scissor
1	2	
1	3	Pull string to close scissor
2	1	Crank arm to move device
2	2	Pull string

For instance, seen in Table 24, participant 1 has three sketches but only addresses PP1 with one solution fragment. Therefore, one is given a variety score. This is seen in the highlighted cell in Table 25. As for participant 2, the value of two is given because two solution fragments were used to address requirement across a set of ideas.

Table 25 An example of Variety score table for PP1

Problem statement	Traditional	Contextual
1	1	0
2	1	1
1	1	1
0	3	1
0	1	1
1	2	0
0	0	0
0	0	1
0	1	1
1	1	2
2	0	1
0	0	2
0	2	2
1	1	1
0	0	0
1	1	2
	0	
	3	
	1	
	2	

For the same reason as for novelty, the analysis was conducted per requirements. Therefore, twenty-four ANOVA tests were performed (10 for problem A, 10 for problem B, 1 comparing A and B, 1 for each problem, 1 overall test for variety). In overall test, problem A and B are combined based on the experimental condition.

3.5.2 Variety Result

A summary table of the ANOVA ($\alpha=0.05$), and a mean comparison between the Problem Statement group (P), the Traditional Requirement Representation group (T), and the Contextual Requirement Representation group (C) for all the requirements is shown in Table 26. If the p-value is less than the

significant level of 0.05, then a post-hoc Fisher's LSD analysis is performed.

Table 26: Summary table for ANOVA for Variety

Test Number	Problem	Requirements	P-value	Comparison of Mean
1	A	WD1	0.352	P>T>C
2	A	WD2	0.089	C>P>T
3	A	WD3	-	-
4	A	WD4	0.428	P>C=T
5	A	WD5	0.039	C>T>P
6	A	WD6	0.766	C>T>P
7	A	WD7	0.483	P>T>C
8	A	WD8	0.114	C>T>P
9	A	WD9	0.404	C>T>P
10	A	WD10	0.442	C>P>T
11	B	PP1	0.265	T>C>P
12	B	PP2	0.777	C>T>P
13	B	PP3	0.480	C>T>P
14	B	PP4	0.697	C>T>P
15	B	PP5	0.518	C>P>T
16	B	PP6	0.032	T>P>C
17	B	PP7	-	-
18	B	PP8	0.424	C>T>P
19	B	PP9	0.549	C>T>P
20	B	PP10	0.325	C>T>P
21	A	All	0.378	C>P>T
22	B	All	0.196	C>T>P
23	A to B	All	0.200	-
24	A + B	All	0.188	C>T>P

There is no statical significance difference in twenty-two out of the twenty-four ANOVAs performed. Two tests with a significant difference were for requirements WD5 (p-value of 0.0393) and PP6 (p-value of 0.0317). It is shown by ANOVA tests that there is no statistical difference between problems (p-value of 0.200) and between experimental condition (p-value of 0.188). A post-hoc Fisher's LSD analysis is conducted to determine which pair is significantly different, and the result of LSD analysis is shown in Table 27.

Table 27: Variety LSD Analysis summary

Difference of Levels	WD5 P-Value	PP6 P-Value
Traditional – Problem Statement	0.236	0.038
Contextual – Problem Statement	0.011	0.760
Contextual – Traditional	0.164	0.011

For WD5, it is concluded that there is a statistical difference between the Contextual and Problem Statement representations. However, the Traditional representation of requirements is not statistically different from the Contextual representation and Problem Statement representation. Unlike WD5, the Traditional representation of requirements is different from both the Contextual and the Problem Statement conditions for PP6. Also, the Contextual and the Problem Statement conditions are not statistically different.

Table 28 Data summary of the overall Variety

Groups	Count	Sum	Average	Variance
Problem Statement	35	168	4.80	7.58

Traditional	37	197	5.32	7.34
Contextual	32	195	6.09	10.2

For the overall variety, there was no significant difference between any of the experimental conditions. However, the Contextual representation averages 6.09 solution fragments per participant for a set of ideas, while the Traditional and the Problem Statement averages 5.32 and 4.80 fragments per participant, respectively.

4 KEY FINDINGS

Base on the analysis, having different representations does have an impact on concept generation. It is determined that the Contextual representation leads to a better novelty and variety of solution fragments in the conceptual sketch. The Contextual representation performed similarly to Traditional representation in the addressment of requirements and the quantity of sketches generated. However, it did not perform as well as the Traditional and the Problem Statement conditions in sketch detail, but the differences are not statistically different. The Traditional representation outperformed the Problem Statement condition in variety and addressment. They both behaved similarly in novelty and sketch detail. However, the Problem Statement yielded the best results for the quantity of sketches.

4.1 Quantity

Overall, having a different representation of requirements has no significant impact on the number of sketches generated between all the test conditions. However, by average, the problem statement condition, where requirements are embedded into the problem statement, does increase the quantity of the concept generated. But it does not improve the quality of the solution. It may be that the problem statement group was only given five requirements (embedded in the problem statement) as opposed to the traditional and the contextual conditions with ten requirements. For the same reason, it has increased the quantity of sketches. Having fewer constraints might allow for greater design space or larger solution space. The finding is in line with previous studies where it was shown having fewer requirements or non-functional requirements generated a greater number of sketches [41]. Having a greater number of sketches did not address more requirements, generated more novel requirements, or created a greater variety of requirements. The assertion that more sketches (higher quantity) lead to better performance against the other metrics should be studied further in the future.

4.2 Addressment

Having requirements embedded within the problem statement does impact the concept generated negatively in terms of the "quality" of the solution. However, there is not enough evidence to conclude if the contextual requirement representation is better than the traditional representation of requirements. However, it is important to note it does not impact negatively in terms of addressment of requirements. As stated for quantity, having five requirements means fewer constraints. It also means that participants were unaware of the other five requirements provided to the Contextual and the Traditional groups. However, it was observed that participants in the problem statement group were addressing requirements that were not given to them. It does prove

that eliciting requirement from sketches may increase the number of requirements considered, as found in [17]. However, the Contextual requirement averaged higher than the traditional and the problem statement groups. It may be due to the justification provided within the requirement for contextual representation. It may motivate individuals to address more requirements, through a more empathetic description of the need.

4.3 Sketch Detail

The finding suggests that there was no statistically significant difference between any of the conditions was found. It indicates no additional work is required with a different representation. On average, contextual did result in lower sketch detail value. However, when visually observed, no difference can be identified. It is important to note that the metric of sketch detail is sensitive to any changes. It was found that if the image is resized 2.5 times or 0.3 times the original size the value of sketch detail becomes inaccurate. Figure 5 shows the effect of multiple size factors for the two different images where 1 and 2 represent different images.

Figure 5: Sensitivity of Sketch Detailing metric

Though not reported, based on visual observation, it can be concluded that all of the sketches are rated between one to three for the complexity metric [34] against the sketch. It does suggest that no difference between the sketches visually; however, sketch detail value analysis suggests that on average contextual representation requires less detail of sketch to generate a solution that score higher in the other metrics.

4.4 Novelty and Variety

For novelty, it was concluded that there was a significant difference between different representations. The contextual representation of requirements outperforms the problem statement and the traditional representation of requirements for generating more novel concept fragments. However, no difference was found for variety based on different representations. It does follow the finding found in novelty where the contextual representation yields a greater number of solution fragments per participant. On average, the participants from the contextual group produce 37.9% of their fragments per participant were novel, while the traditional representation results in 26.9% of its solution fragments per participant as novel closely followed by the problem statement group with 26% of novel solution per participant. Thus, the addition of a contextual representation of requirements in the

traditional design process can benefit the overall design in terms of generating novel and variety of solution fragments. It yields a unique and innovative design for a problem. It may be because the additional information in contextual requirements motivates the users to generate a greater variety of solution fragments and novel solution fragments.

Table 29: Percentage of novel solution per participant

Novelty and variety	Novel Fragment	Total Solution Fragment	Percentage
Contextual	2.31	6.09	37.93
Traditional	1.43	5.32	26.87
Problem Statement	1.25	4.8	26.04

5 CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, the contextual representation generated greater quality of work with higher novelty and variety of solution fragments and addressed more requirements per sketch. It is important to note that there is no adverse effect on the number of concept sketches generated by having contextual requirements or traditional requirements, as ANOVA has shown that they are statistically equivalent. Also, an impact of having a greater number of sketches was not found on any other aspect of the solution in terms of addressment, sketch detail, novelty, and variety. Contextual representation can help designers generate more creative and unique solutions. Therefore, innovation in the product can take place if Contextual representation is used.

Due to COVID-19, this study was conducted via online surveys. Thus, the researchers were unable to directly control the experiment as well as if it were conducted in a traditional classroom setting. There was little control over whether the participants read all directions thoroughly, whereas in a classroom-based study, at least the instructions could have been read aloud. This was evident in cases where participants were asked to use copy paper to eliminate foreseen complication in sketch detail metric analysis. Another reason the survey posed a challenge was the inability of participants to go back, as some of them did skip the question. Therefore, it is not known if all of the requirements were read by the participants.

This study does pose some questions that can be looked at for future work. Several idea generation tools, such as brainstorming, the 6-3-5 method, or storyboarding, require the designer to consider requirements and problem statements during their use. Further, these activities might be done multiple times for different aspects of the overall problem across multiple weeks, as in the case of scrum sprints. Therefore, can contextual representations help designers retain these requirements across time beyond the duration of the activity? If this is the case, then a more efficient and effective design process may be achieved such that the designers do not need to continually return to the documented requirements to be reminded of the problem and task at hand. Further, it might be of interest to determine whether this contextualized representation has similar influence and impact on idea generation tools that employ textual descriptions of the solution space.

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